

Management of *Ahiputana* (Diper Rash) in an Infant with application of Shatdhauta Ghruta A single case study

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Abstract

Ayurveda is an ancient medical science which deals with the swasthya or normal health of human being as well as wide description regarding various diseases and their treatment. Diaper rash is a common problem in pediatric OPD. Prevalence of Diaper rash has been variably reported from 7-35% in the first one year of life. Most cases occurs between 9-12 month of age. It is caused by improper care of infants and children requiring diapering. Ayurveda clearly states that main Hetu (cause) of Ahiputana is Stanyadushthi. ⁽³⁾ The disease is characterized by Pidika (papulovesicular lesion), Kandu (Irritability due to itching), Strava(discharge),Varna(skin color over perianal region) etc.

Keywords; Ahiputana; Shatdhauth ghruta; Ayurveda; Kaumarbhriya; Diper rash

1. Introduction

Ayurveda has described the unique principle of *tridosha, dhatus, mala* for the homeostasis of the body. Kaumarbhriya is the branch that deals with the mother and child relationship and there health, it also deals with kumarabharana, dhatri, kshirdosha, dushta stanya, ghahadosha and their treatment. Diaper rash arising due to dushta stanyapana, *asuchita* (unhygienic condition) such as *kuparicharya* of child in which mother fails to keep perianal region dry, clean timely after every mala, mutra visarjana ".1". If mother fails to keep proper care of her child then they may suffer from many diseases and Ahiputana is one of them Diaper rash is one of the most common skin disorder in infant and children. According to Acharya Vagbhata due to *Malopalepa* (after defecation and urination) or due to *swadatwa, kaphsdosha* and *raktadhatu* get aggravated to procedure *Tamravarni vrana* at gudpradesh ".2". For newborns and toddlers, diaper rashes are a frequent skin problem. They may create red splotches and scales in the vaginal region as well as on the bottom of the infant. Rashes may spread up the child's legs and tummy in certain circumstances. Diaper rashes are quite prevalent because they thrive in warm, humid environments. As a result, a diaper is an ideal environment for the rash to grow.

Stool and urine irritate the skin. If your infant has frequent bowel movements, he or she may be more prone to diaper rash. A rash may be caused by tight-fitting diapers or clothes that rub against the skin. A new brand of disposable diapers or a detergent, bleach, or fabric softener used to wash cloth diapers may cause your baby's skin to react. Ingredients present in various infant creams, powders, and oils are among the other chemicals that might exacerbate the condition. Infection caused by bacteria or yeast. What starts off as a simple skin infection may quickly spread across the surrounding area because it's warm and damp. New foods are being introduced. The content of a baby's feces changes when he or she begins to ingest solid meals.

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Diaper rash is more likely as a result of this. Changes in your baby’s nutrition may cause more frequent feces, which may cause diaper rash.

1.1. Case study

Aims and objective - To evaluate the role of Ayurvedic Regimen in the management of Ahiputana (Napkin rash).

2. Material and methods

- **Study design**- Present study is a single case study conducted in the department of Kaumarbhritya of Government Ayurved college and hospital Baramati District pune. Maharashtra, India.
- **Case report**- A 10 months old male patient came in Kaumarbhritya OPD in Government Ayurved college and hospital Baramati District pune. Maharashtra, India. With a complaints of loose stools, irritability, redness of perianal region with rashes itching and severity increases during passing frequent loose stools
- **History of present illness**-Patient was healthy before 5 days back But gradually he suffered with loose stools episodes 6 to 7 from 2 days and further that on anal region development of rashes with redness and itching in perianal region. Recurrent episodes of – loose stool

Associated complaints- Irritability, excess cry

- **History of past illness**- – H/O Introduction of new foods with poor sanitization. No H/O any other major illness or any surgery.
- **Drug history** – No significant
- **Family History**- Not significant
- **Birth history** –
 - Antenatal – nonspecific
 - Natal – Full Term Normal Delivery, at civil hospital, Baby Cried Immediately After Birth, birth wt. – 2.4 kg.
 - Postnatal – No H/O neonatal jaundice & seizure no H/O NICU Admission.

2.1. General Examination

Table 1 Examination

Built	Moderate
General appearance	Fair
Temp.	98.7 °F
Pulse	118/min
RR	30/min
Height	62cm
Weight	7.8kg

2.2. Physical Examination

- Nadi - Kapahapradhan
- Mala -mala pravrutti
- Mutra - Samyakpravrutti
- Jivha - Sama
- Shabda - Spashta
- Sparsha - Samshitoshna
- Druk – Mild pallor
- Aakruti - Madhyam

2.3. Treatment Plan Shatdhauta Ghruta

An application of Shatdhauta ghruta- viscous layer of *Shatdhauta ghruta* applied on a perianal region 4 to 5 times in a day and avoid wearing of diaper upto the healing from rashes.

Figure 1 After application of Shatdhaut ghruta treatment

Table 2 Observation and result

Observation	Before Treatment	After Completion of regimen
Kandu	+++	-
Pidika (Skin lesions)	++	+
Shipran sphotam (Blister)	+	-
Strava (Discharge)	++	-
Daha (Burning sensation)	+++	-
Irritability	+++	-
Tamravrna (Redness)	+++	+
Note: + mild, ++moderate, +++ severe , - no symptoms present		

2.4. Histopathological report

Table 3 Change of reports after application of shatdhaut ghruta

Investigations	Before Treatment	After Treatment
TLC	13100/cu mm	8000/cu mm
DLC		
Neutrophils	79%	65%
Lymphocytes	18%	26%
Eosinophills	01%	01%
Monocytes	03%	05%
Hb%	10.7 gm %	10.9gm %

3. Discussion

In the Ayurvedic system of medicine, ghee plays a vital role, both as a vehicle to deliver the active constituent and a base for incorporating active components to formulate the dosage forms. Ayurveda also supports the coadministration of ghee along with other remedial treatments. For example, Brahmi ghruta for cognitive function; Vasa ghruta for the respiratory system; Shatadhauta ghruta for skin diseases, Bhallatakadi ghruta for wound healing ".3". ".4". Shata-dhauta-

ghrita (SDG) washed cow ghee 100 time with water (shata = one hundred, dhauta = washed). Traditional texts mention it for treating burns, chicken pox, scars, wounds, herpes, leprosy, and other skin diseases, as well as as a vehicle for drugs to be applied externally. “.5”. The Ayurvedic preparation was evaluated for its physicochemical parameters in the study, and changes that occurred during washing were investigated. An attempt is made to find out the rationale behind washing cow ghee 100 times with water. The characteristic odour and granular, oily consistency of cow ghee are not present in shata dhauta ghrita, and so it is a homogeneous, smooth, non-oily product that is easier to apply so Patient compliance is thus improved. When compared to the acidic pH value of ghee, the neutral pH of shata dhauta ghrita makes it beneficial by preventing skin irritation. Because of the smaller particle size of shata dhauta ghrita, the product is non-granular, non-sticky, and homogeneous, making it easy to apply to the skin and possibly increasing the rate of absorption through the skin. Washing results in a homogeneous oil-in-water emulsion with better consistency and viscosity, which makes it suitable for use in topical application.

4. Conclusion

Ahiputana is a disease comparable with diaper rash. It is common disease in observed in infantile age due to low socio economic condition, poor sanitation. Ahiputana is a separate disease mentioned in Kshudraroga by Acharya having its own etiology, pathology and management. In Ayurveda literature *Maloplepa*, *Asuchitwa*, *Dushtastanyapana hetu* are described of Ahiputana. But *Asuchitwa* is more common *hetu*. Both Kapha and Rakta have been considered to be the chief Doshas and Rakta Dusthi caused by aggravation Pitta, hence Pitta also involved in the pathogenesis of Ahiputna. The symptoms of Ahiputana described in text are *Tamravarnata*, *Kandu* (irritability), *Strava*, *Pidaka* are seen in present study. Hence application of *Shatdhauta Ghruta* is very useful and unique gifts of ayurveda for diper rash in infants.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from both parents of infant participants included in the study.

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